

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2KA53201	2KA53206	2KA53207	2KA53208	2KA53209	2KA53210	2KA53211	2KA53211R	2KA53212	2KA53220	2KA53222	2KA53223	2KA53224
Arachnida	Araneae	Anyphaenidae	<i>Anyphaena</i>	<i>accentuata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Aculepeira</i>	<i>ceropegia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Araneus</i>	<i>diadematus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Araneus</i>	<i>marmoreus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Araneus</i>	<i>quadratus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Araniella</i>	<i>cucurbitina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Cyclosa</i>	<i>conica</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Gibbaranea</i>	<i>omoeda</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Larinioides</i>	<i>patagiatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Zygiella</i>	<i>dispar</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Zygiella</i>	<i>montana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i>	<i>erraticum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona</i>	<i>caerulescens</i>	0	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona</i>	<i>comta</i>	95	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona</i>	<i>pallidula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Cybaeidae	<i>Cryphoea</i>	<i>silvicola</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Dictynidae	<i>Dictyna</i>	<i>arundinacea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Dictynidae	<i>Lathys</i>	<i>humilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Gnaphosidae	<i>Callilepis</i>	<i>nocturna</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Gnaphosidae	<i>Gnaphosa</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Gnaphosidae	<i>Gnaphosa</i>	<i>petrobia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1411	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Gnaphosidae	<i>Gnaphosa</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Agyneta</i>	<i>innotabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Bolyphantes</i>	<i>alticeps</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Bolyphantes</i>	<i>luteolus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Centromerita</i>	<i>concinna</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Drapetisca</i>	<i>socialis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Helophora</i>	<i>orinoma</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Lepthyphantes</i>	<i>minutus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Microlinyphia</i>	<i>pusilla</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Moebelia</i>	<i>penicillata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Obscuriphantes</i>	<i>obscurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Pityohyphantes</i>	<i>phrygianus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Pocadicnemis</i>	<i>juncea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Tenuiphantes</i>	<i>mengei</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	78
Arachnida	Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Tenuiphantes</i>	<i>zimmermanni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Lycosidae	<i>Alopecosa</i>	<i>trabalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i>		0	0	0	0	0	111	0	17	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Araneae	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i>	<i>albatula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2KA53201	2KA53206	2KA53207	2KA53208	2KA53209	2KA53210	2KA53211	2KA53211R	2KA53212	2KA53220	2KA53222	2KA53223	2KA53224
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	617	0	0	0	7	0	1793	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	483	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	0	617	589	224	0	11	28	0	0	0	23	4291
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	39	0	0	1824	0	30	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1085	179	0	303
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	13866	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	0	0	0	0	0	40	0	0	116	393	129	200	79
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimarinimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	7	0	9213	144	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	0	0	209	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2KA53225	2KA53226	2KA53227	2KA53228	2KA53229	2KA53230	2KA53233	2KA53234	2KA53235	2KA53240	2KA53242	2Z80702	2Z80703
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Simulium</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Simulium</i>	<i>armoricanum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Simulium</i>	<i>aureum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Simulium</i>	<i>urbanum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sphaeroceridae	<i>Leptocera</i>	<i>fontinalis</i>	0	0	0	84	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae			18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Dasysyrphus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Dasysyrphus</i>	<i>albostrigatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Dasysyrphus</i>	<i>occidualis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Dasysyrphus</i>	<i>tricinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Epistrophe</i>	<i>grossulariae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Episyrphus</i>	<i>balteatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Eristalis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Eristalis</i>	<i>similis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Eristalis</i>	<i>tenax</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Eupeodes</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Eupeodes</i>	<i>corollae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Meliscaeva</i>	<i>cinctella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Merodon</i>	<i>caerulescens</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Parasyrphus</i>	<i>vittiger</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Pipizella</i>	<i>viduata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Platycheirus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Sphaerophoria</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Sphaerophoria</i>	<i>interrupta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Syrphus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Syrphus</i>	<i>opinator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Syrphus</i>	<i>torvus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tabanidae	<i>Haematopota</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2534	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tabanidae	<i>Hybomitra</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Acemya</i>	<i>acuticornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Blepharomyia</i>	<i>piliceps</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Campylocheta</i>	<i>praecox</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Cyzenis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Cyzenis</i>	<i>albicans</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Eriothrix</i>	<i>rufomaculata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Gymnocheta</i>	<i>lucida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	657	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Lydina</i>	<i>aenea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Pales</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Phytomyptera</i>	<i>nigrina</i>	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Platymya</i>	<i>fimbriata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	272	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2KA53225	2KA53226	2KA53227	2KA53228	2KA53229	2KA53230	2KA53233	2KA53234	2KA53235	2KA53240	2KA53242	2Z80702	2Z80703
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	2148	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4358	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8631	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	690	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			403	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	306	4	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	16	13062	2	11101	0	1152	0	0	1028	38	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			1006	0	0	360	0	441	0	83	0	11	5	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		3733	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	55	45	454	85	52	0	0	42465	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	143	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	455	77
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	0	4721	0	52	0	0	0	0	0	17

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80704	2Z80710	2Z80711	2Z80713	2Z80714	2Z80715	2Z80734	2Z80734R	2Z80736	2Z80737	2Z80738	2Z80739	2Z80740
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorp	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryom	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryom	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatid				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	329	0	0	0	0
Insecta					43	7	12	879	4152	87	856	131	13	7	377	14	952
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera				0	0	0	2317	0	0	33701	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	4480	0	3694	0	221	43347	0	0	0	0	131	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80704	2Z80710	2Z80711	2Z80713	2Z80714	2Z80715	2Z80734	2Z80734R	2Z80736	2Z80737	2Z80738	2Z80739	2Z80740
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Anatis</i>	<i>ocellata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>quatuordecim</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Calvia</i>	<i>uttata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>oblongoguttat</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Myzia</i>	<i>a</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Anthonomus</i>	<i>phyllocola</i>	0	11	0	16	0	0	1141	16261	0	0	6	5	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachonyx</i>	<i>pineti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachyderes</i>	<i>incanus</i>	0	0	0	234	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Cleopomiarus</i>	<i>graminis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroctonus</i>	<i>terebrans</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hylastes</i>	<i>brunneus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hypera</i>	<i>nigrirostris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>linearis</i>	0	41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2023	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>memnonia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>pauxillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>singularis</i>	0	0	0	353	0	0	0	28	0	0	220	0	4212
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pachylobius</i>	<i>picivorus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Phyllobius</i>	<i>argentatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pissodes</i>	<i>validirostris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>cervinus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Rhamphus</i>	<i>pulicarius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>melanogrammu</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>m</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Tomicus</i>	<i>piniperda</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Trachyphloeus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Xylosandrus</i>	<i>crassiusculus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Dermestidae	<i>Thyrodrias</i>	<i>contractus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Limoniscus</i>	<i>violaceus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Melanotus</i>	<i>villosus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>	<i>dorsalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Enicopus</i>	<i>pilosus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Oedemeridae	<i>Chrysanthia</i>	<i>viridissima</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Ptinidae	<i>Anobium</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Anobiidae	<i>Ernobius</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80704	2Z80710	2Z80711	2Z80713	2Z80714	2Z80715	2Z80734	2Z80734R	2Z80736	2Z80737	2Z80738	2Z80739	2Z80740
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Spilogona</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Spilogona</i>	<i>novemmaculata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Thricops</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Thricops</i>	<i>cunctans</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Cordyla</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Cordyla</i>	<i>brevicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Exechia</i>	<i>dorsalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Exechia</i>	<i>fusca</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Exechiopsis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Mycetophila</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Mycetophila</i>	<i>alea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Mycetophila</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Mycetophilidae	<i>Mycomya</i>	<i>fuscata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Phoridae	<i>Megaselia</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	142	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Phoridae	<i>Megaselia</i>	<i>differens</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Phoridae	<i>Megaselia</i>	<i>ignobilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	56	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Pipunculidae	<i>Chalarus</i>	<i>decorus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Pipunculidae	<i>Chalarus</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Pipunculidae	<i>Eudorylas</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Pipunculidae	<i>Tomosvaryella</i>	<i>kuthyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Pipunculidae	<i>Tomosvaryella</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Polleniidae	<i>Pollenia</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Polleniidae	<i>Pollenia</i>	<i>labialis</i>	0	0	53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Polleniidae	<i>Pollenia</i>	<i>vagabunda</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sarcophagidae	<i>Angiometopa</i>	<i>falleni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sarcophagidae	<i>Blaesoxipha</i>	<i>laticornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sarcophagidae	<i>Ravinia</i>	<i>pernix</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>cinerascens</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>iridipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>nocturna</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>odoriphaga</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>pauperata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Leptosciarella</i>	<i>hirtipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Scatopsciara</i>	<i>nana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Scatopsciara</i>	<i>simillima</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Trichosia</i>	<i>edwardsi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sciomyzidae	<i>Pherbellia</i>	<i>cinerella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sepsidae	<i>Sepsis</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Sepsidae	<i>Sepsis</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Prosimulium</i>	<i>hirtipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Simuliidae	<i>Prosimulium</i>	<i>latimucro</i>	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80704	2Z80710	2Z80711	2Z80713	2Z80714	2Z80715	2Z80734	2Z80734R	2Z80736	2Z80737	2Z80738	2Z80739	2Z80740
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	117	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	2	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	11	313	99	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	168	0	5
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	71	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	0	0	109	0	135	91	0	0	212	0	0	55	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	0	30	0	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	85	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80742	2Z80743	2Z80744	2Z80745	2Z80746	2Z80747	2Z80748	2Z80749	2Z80751	2Z80753	2Z80754	2Z80755	2Z80756	2Z80757
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorp	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryom	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryom	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatid				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	163	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta					131	79	237	27	0	21	52	7	28	232	5	170	0	287
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	17	59	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	0	0	0	54	0	0	0	0	0	62	16	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80742	2Z80743	2Z80744	2Z80745	2Z80746	2Z80747	2Z80748	2Z80749	2Z80751	2Z80753	2Z80754	2Z80755	2Z80756	2Z80757
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	3064	0	135	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	324	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			14	67	3306	0	0	0	0	0	5	38	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	146	37	45	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	163	0	0	0	60	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0	159
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	0	0	0	0	142	0	0	0	0	0	3622	67	0	10581
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	0	0	65	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	28150	0	533	78	0	63	0	52	1013	0	27	1023	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80742	2Z80743	2Z80744	2Z80745	2Z80746	2Z80747	2Z80748	2Z80749	2Z80751	2Z80753	2Z80754	2Z80755	2Z80756	2Z80757
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae	<i>Erebia</i>	<i>euryale</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae	<i>Erebia</i>	<i>oeme</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Oecophoridae	<i>Crassa</i>	<i>bractella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Oecophoridae	<i>Oecophora</i>	<i>trictella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Dahlica</i>	<i>triquetrella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Epichnopterix</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Epichnopterix</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Taleporia</i>	<i>tubulosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pterophoridae	<i>Merrifieldia</i>	<i>leucodactyla</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Dioryctria</i>	<i>simplicella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	239	0	0	22	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Pempelia</i>	<i>palumbella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Phycitodes</i>	<i>saxicola</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Scythrididae	<i>Scythris</i>	<i>obscura</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Scythrididae	<i>Scythris</i>	<i>picaepennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae			0	0	0	0	65	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>	<i>myrtilana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>	<i>unguicella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Archips</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Argyrotaenia</i>	<i>ljungiana</i>	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3039	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Clavigesta</i>	<i>purdeyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	149	0	46	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Cnephasia</i>	<i>alticolana</i>	0	0	91	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epagoge</i>	<i>grotiana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>bilunana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>ramella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>tetraquetra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma</i>	<i>dealbana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma</i>	<i>sociana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Pandemis</i>	<i>cerasana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Pandemis</i>	<i>heparana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia</i>	<i>pinicolana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia</i>	<i>pinivorana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	289	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Syndemis</i>	<i>musculana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Yponomeutidae	<i>Cedestis</i>	<i>subfasciella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Yponomeutidae	<i>Ocnerostoma</i>	<i>pinariella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	14	0	0	1237	0	7167
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Ypsolophidae	<i>Ypsolopha</i>	<i>parenthesella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena</i>	<i>filipendulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena</i>	<i>trifolii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Nineta</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	138	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80758	2Z80759	2Z80762	2Z80763	2Z80764	2Z80766	2Z80769	2Z80770	2Z80771	2Z80772	2Z80773	2Z80774	2Z80775	2Z80776
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorpha	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatida				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta					0	229	184	62	278	753	138	5	518	4	815	624	0	150
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera				0	0	36	112	0	11	0	0	91	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	89	0	357	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80758	2Z80759	2Z80762	2Z80763	2Z80764	2Z80766	2Z80769	2Z80770	2Z80771	2Z80772	2Z80773	2Z80774	2Z80775	2Z80776
Insecta	Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Rheocricotopus</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Smittia</i>	<i>pratorum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Smittia</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Zavrelimyia</i>	<i>melanura</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chloropidae	<i>Hapleginella</i>	<i>laevifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chloropidae	<i>Oscinella</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Chloropidae	<i>Oscinella</i>	<i>sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35
Insecta	Diptera	Culicidae	<i>Aedes</i>	<i>pullatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Culicidae	<i>Culex</i>	<i>hortensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Dolichopodidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Drosophilidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Drosophilidae	<i>Drosophila</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Drosophilidae	<i>Drosophila</i>	<i>suzukii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Drosophilidae	<i>Scaptomyza</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Empididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Empididae	<i>Empis</i>	<i>univittata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Empididae	<i>Rhamphomyia</i>	<i>spinipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Empididae	<i>Rhamphomyia</i>	<i>sulcata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Ephydriidae	<i>Lamproscatella</i>	<i>brunnipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Heleomyzidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Heleomyzidae	<i>Scoliocentra</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Hybotidae	<i>Ethyneura</i>	<i>myrtilli</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Hybotidae	<i>Tachydromia</i>	<i>annulimana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Limoniidae	<i>Dicranomyia</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Limoniidae	<i>Dicranomyia</i>	<i>didyma</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Limoniidae	<i>Limonia</i>	<i>sylvicola</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Limoniidae	<i>Orimarga</i>	<i>attenuata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Lonchopteridae	<i>Lonchoptera</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Coenosia</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Coenosia</i>	<i>means</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>	<i>impuncta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>	<i>pubiseta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>	<i>reversio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Hydrotaea</i>	<i>armipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Lispocephala</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Mesembrina</i>	<i>meridiana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Musca</i>	<i>autumnalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Phaonia</i>	<i>meigeni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Polietes</i>	<i>domitor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80758	2Z80759	2Z80762	2Z80763	2Z80764	2Z80766	2Z80769	2Z80770	2Z80771	2Z80772	2Z80773	2Z80774	2Z80775	2Z80776
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	214	0	0	0	0	0	581	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	78	6	6
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	15	0	0	59	0	0	12	0	0	0	2434
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	0	0	60	0	0	141	0	0	9	37128	0	33	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	344	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	13	6	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	73	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	115	42	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	224	0	88	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	58	496	342	0	0	321	20176	52	95	0	308	0	56	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimarinimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	129	7964	0	0	3567	0	82	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80777	2Z80778	2Z80779	2Z80783	2Z80784	2Z80785	2Z80786	2Z80787	2Z80788	2Z80789	2Z80791	2Z80792	2Z80794
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	268999	0	0	107	0	0	0	341	0	0	218	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	3495	0	2	0	0	0	0	22	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			3	83	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	163	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	5	0	10	0	0	0	57	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	219	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	56	1949	0	3176	119109	10029	314	64888	191	0	0	119	266
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	69	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	18	0	0	58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	414	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	19	0	0	25641	984	1067	3240	82	0	920	58426	144	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80795	2Z80805	2Z80807	2Z80812	2Z80813	2Z80814	2Z80815	2Z80816	2Z80818	2Z80819	2Z80820	2Z80821	2Z80822
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorpha	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	682	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatida				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta					13	12	0	279	136	2164	0	14	58	18	21	34	289
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80795	2Z80805	2Z80807	2Z80812	2Z80813	2Z80814	2Z80815	2Z80816	2Z80818	2Z80819	2Z80820	2Z80821	2Z80822
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Anatis</i>	<i>ocellata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>quatuordecim</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Calvia</i>	<i>uttata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>oblongoguttat</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Myzia</i>	<i>a</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Anthonomus</i>	<i>phyllocola</i>	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	17
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachonyx</i>	<i>pineti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachyderes</i>	<i>incanus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Cleopomiarus</i>	<i>graminis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroctonus</i>	<i>terebrans</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hylastes</i>	<i>brunneus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hypera</i>	<i>nigrirostris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>linearis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>memnonia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>pauillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>singularis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pachylobius</i>	<i>picivorus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Phyllobius</i>	<i>argentatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pissodes</i>	<i>validirostris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>cervinus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Rhamphus</i>	<i>pulicarius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>melanogrammu</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>m</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Tomicus</i>	<i>piniperda</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Trachyphloeus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Xylosandrus</i>	<i>crassiusculus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Dermestidae	<i>Thylogrias</i>	<i>contractus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Limoniscus</i>	<i>violaceus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Melanotus</i>	<i>villosus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>	<i>dorsalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Enicopus</i>	<i>pilosus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Oedemeridae	<i>Chrysanthia</i>	<i>viridissima</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Ptinidae	<i>Anobium</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Anobiidae	<i>Ernobius</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80795	2Z80805	2Z80807	2Z80812	2Z80813	2Z80814	2Z80815	2Z80816	2Z80818	2Z80819	2Z80820	2Z80821	2Z80822
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	86	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	179	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	16	60	0	46683	0	26	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	96
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	7871	22328	88243	9656	2121	6632	28550	8928	5843	55276	102677	69447	36024
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1324	0	0	0	0	80	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	329	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	671	0	634	0	42	4437	0	0	1721	194

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80823	3Y03503	3Y03504	3Y03505	3Y03506	3Y03507	3Y03508	3Y03510	3Y03511	3Y03519	3Y03546	3Y03547	3Y03548
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorpha	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatida				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta					0	0	18	4636	81	546	101	32	693	52723	73	171	161
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera				0	0	0	3461	0	0	0	0	0	12059	13276	5253	90
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	64	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	88	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	0	0	5572	0	0	0	0	0	16015	18821	6841	125

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	2Z80823	3Y03503	3Y03504	3Y03505	3Y03506	3Y03507	3Y03508	3Y03510	3Y03511	3Y03519	3Y03546	3Y03547	3Y03548
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	54	0	0	0	0	0	248	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	996	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	28	0	0	0	0	0	438	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	0	165	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	46
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	154	0	0	100	119	0	236	57	88	0	0	0	13
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	15	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	1548	6119	0	154	31	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	61	518	82	1644

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03549	3Y03550	3Y03551	3Y03552	3Y03553	3Y03555	3Y03556	3Y03557	3Y03558	3Y03559	3Y03560	3Y03562	3Y03563
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Cunaxidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Phytoptidae			0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arachnida	Trombidiforme	Tetranychidae	<i>Oligonychus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chilopoda	Lithobiomorpha	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>minor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Chordeumatida				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Glomerida	Glomeridae	<i>Glomeris</i>	<i>intermedia</i>	0	0	91	0	0	0	1075	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Julida	Julidae	<i>Cylindroiulus</i>	<i>londinensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diplopoda	Polydesmida	Polydesmidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	125	0	0
Diplopoda	Polyxenida	Polyxenidae	<i>Polyxenus</i>	<i>lagurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta					803	990	1010	1130	0	19	0	465	104	7	249	59	59
Insecta	Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta</i>	<i>fuliginosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>pilula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	3051	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Byrrhidae	<i>Byrrhus</i>	<i>figurata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>livida</i>	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Cantharis</i>	<i>tristis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cantharidae	<i>Rhagonycha</i>	<i>fuscitibia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Amara</i>	<i>bifrons</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calathus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Calodromius</i>	<i>spilotus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i>	<i>pumilio</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Anastrangalia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>sartor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus</i>	<i>titillator</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Oxymirus</i>	<i>cursor</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>rubra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Donacia</i>	<i>clavipes</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Cimberididae	<i>Doydirhynchus</i>	<i>austriacus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	3996	0	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03549	3Y03550	3Y03551	3Y03552	3Y03553	3Y03555	3Y03556	3Y03557	3Y03558	3Y03559	3Y03560	3Y03562	3Y03563
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	352	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	66	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35511	87	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	146	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	458	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	122	75	13	0	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			6	1249	0	65	102	0	0	0	0	0	136	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>luculentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	168	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	57	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	93	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4149	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	0	136	0	0	0	0	0	95	111	0	0	144	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	124	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	8280	95626	34	29539	4132	98	0	0	0	26	0	0	35
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	5	0	0	0	0	31	0	0	59	0	131	116	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03549	3Y03550	3Y03551	3Y03552	3Y03553	3Y03555	3Y03556	3Y03557	3Y03558	3Y03559	3Y03560	3Y03562	3Y03563
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Crambidae	<i>Platytes</i>	<i>cerussella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Crambidae	<i>Scoparia</i>	<i>pyralella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Depressariidae	<i>Depressaria</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Depressariidae	<i>Semioscopis</i>	<i>avellanella</i>	0	166	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Drepanidae	<i>Ochropacha</i>	<i>duplaris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Erebidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Erebidae	<i>Arctia</i>	<i>plantaginis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Erebidae	<i>Eilema</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Erebidae	<i>Leucoma</i>	<i>salicis</i>	0	51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Acompsia</i>	<i>cinerella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Aristotelia</i>	<i>ericinella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Carpatolechia</i>	<i>proximella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Hypatima</i>	<i>rhomboidella</i>	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Klimeschiopsis</i>	<i>kiningerella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	<i>Neofaculta</i>	<i>ericetella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>medialbiferaAH</i>													
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Alcis</i>	<i>01Ch</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Alsophila</i>	<i>aescularia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Anticlea</i>	<i>derivata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Boudinotiana</i>	<i>notha</i>	0	122	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Bupalus</i>	<i>pinaria</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Charissa</i>	<i>ambiguata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Chloroclysta</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Colostygia</i>	<i>aptata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Colostygia</i>	<i>turbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	576	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Colotois</i>	<i>pennaria</i>	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Crocota</i>	<i>peletieraria</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Ematurga</i>	<i>amitaria</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Epirrhoe</i>	<i>tristata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Epirrita</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Eulithis</i>	<i>populata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	249	1764	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Eulithis</i>	<i>prunata</i>	0	0	841	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Eupithecia</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Eupithecia</i>	<i>indigata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Eupithecia</i>	<i>pulchellata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Hylaea</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	56720	88	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Lomaspilis</i>	<i>opis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Macaria</i>	<i>brunneata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Macaria</i>	<i>liturata</i>	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	<i>Mesotype</i>	<i>didymata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03564	3Y03565	3Y03566	3Y03567	3Y03568	3Y03569	3Y03570	3Y03571	3Y03572	3Y03573	3Y03574	3Y03575	3Y03601
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Anatis</i>	<i>ocellata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>quatuordecimguttata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Calvia</i>	<i>oblongoguttata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Myzia</i>	<i>a</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Anthonomus</i>	<i>phyllocola</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	3954	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachonyx</i>	<i>pineti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Brachyderes</i>	<i>incanus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Cleopomiarus</i>	<i>graminis</i>	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroctonus</i>	<i>terebrens</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hylastes</i>	<i>brunneus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Hypera</i>	<i>nigrirostris</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>linearis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Magdalis</i>	<i>memnonia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>pauillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>singularis</i>	0	0	37118	0	0	0	93	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pachylobius</i>	<i>picivorus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Phyllobius</i>	<i>argentatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pissodes</i>	<i>validirostris</i>	0	0	180	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>cervinus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Rhamphus</i>	<i>pulicarius</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				<i>melanogrammu</i>													
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>m</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	65	0	77	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Tomicus</i>	<i>piniperda</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Trachyphloeus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Xylosandrus</i>	<i>crassiusculus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Dermestidae	<i>Thyodrias</i>	<i>contractus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Limoniscus</i>	<i>violaceus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Melanotus</i>	<i>villosus</i>	0	0	765	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus</i>	<i>dorsalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Dasytes</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	59	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Enicopus</i>	<i>pilosus</i>	0	0	790	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Oedemeridae	<i>Chrysanthia</i>	<i>viridissima</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Ptinidae	<i>Anobium</i>	<i>fulvicorne</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Coleoptera	Anobiidae	<i>Ernobius</i>	<i>mollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03564	3Y03565	3Y03566	3Y03567	3Y03568	3Y03569	3Y03570	3Y03571	3Y03572	3Y03573	3Y03574	3Y03575	3Y03601
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Triarthria</i>	<i>setipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tachinidae	<i>Trixa</i>	<i>conspersa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Tephritis</i>	<i>araneosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>cingulata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Thereva</i>	<i>handlirschi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>		0	0	1405	0	37	0	0	0	82	105	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>confusa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	166	0	4461	42	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>excisa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>limbata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>rufina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	115	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>scripta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>variicornis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	57	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>varipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Diptera	Xylophagidae	<i>Xylophagus</i>	<i>cingulus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis</i>	<i>cf.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family A			0	18	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Family B			0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Anthocoridae	<i>Temnostethus</i>	<i>pusillus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Acyrtosiphon</i>	<i>malvae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Amphorophora</i>	<i>rubi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Anoecia</i>	<i>corni</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	104	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>farinosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>lugentis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis</i>	<i>sambuci</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Brachycaudus</i>	<i>klugkisti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Callipterinella</i>	<i>calliptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Chaitophorus</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>confinis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>juniperi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	380	24	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pineae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6437	13	0	0	5	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pini</i>	0	0	0	0	0	124	0	0	11419	367	6040	8959	18
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Cinara</i>	<i>pinimaritimae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Corylobium</i>	<i>avellanae</i>	0	0	0	0	28	145	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>betulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Euceraphis</i>	<i>punctipennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Eulachnus</i>	<i>rileyi</i>	0	37	0	22	0	0	0	0	110	301	39	4134	0

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	3Y03564	3Y03565	3Y03566	3Y03567	3Y03568	3Y03569	3Y03570	3Y03571	3Y03572	3Y03573	3Y03574	3Y03575	3Y03601
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae	<i>Erebia</i>	<i>euryale</i>	74	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae	<i>Erebia</i>	<i>oeme</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Oecophoridae	<i>Crassa</i>	<i>bractella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Oecophoridae	<i>Oecophora</i>	<i>bractella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Dahlica</i>	<i>triquetrella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Epichnopterix</i>	<i>sp.1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Epichnopterix</i>	<i>sp.2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Psychidae	<i>Taleporia</i>	<i>tubulosa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pterophoridae	<i>Merrifieldia</i>	<i>leucodactyla</i>	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Dioryctria</i>	<i>simplicella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	32	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Pempelia</i>	<i>palumbella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	<i>Phycitodes</i>	<i>saxicola</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Scythrididae	<i>Scythris</i>	<i>obscura</i>	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Scythrididae	<i>Scythris</i>	<i>picaepennis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>	<i>myrtillana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>	<i>unguicella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Archips</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Argyrotaenia</i>	<i>ljungiana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	218	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Clavigesta</i>	<i>purdeyi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Cnephasia</i>	<i>alticolana</i>	0	0	8423	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epagoge</i>	<i>grotiana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>bilunana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>ramella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia</i>	<i>tetraquetra</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma</i>	<i>dealbana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma</i>	<i>sociana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Pandemis</i>	<i>cerasana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Pandemis</i>	<i>heparana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia</i>	<i>pinicolana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	3878	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia</i>	<i>pinivorana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	<i>Syndemis</i>	<i>musculana</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Yponomeutidae	<i>Cedestis</i>	<i>subfasciella</i>	51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Yponomeutidae	<i>Ocnerostoma</i>	<i>pinariella</i>	0	0	0	0	302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Ypsolophidae	<i>Ypsolopha</i>	<i>parenthesella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena</i>	<i>filipendulae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Lepidoptera	Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena</i>	<i>trifolii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Nineta</i>		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insecta	Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada</i>		0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

